

ON THE RESEARCH OF COMPOSERS' CREATIVITY OF UZBEKISTAN IN THE SPHERE OF CHILDREN'S PIANO MUSIC IN THE CONTEXT OF MUSICAL EDUCATION

Sidikova Aliya Maratovna

Independent researcher, the Institute of Art History of the
Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
Lecturer, Department of Music Art at Andijan State University,
Uzbekistan

Abstract *The purpose of the research. The purpose of this exploration was to provide a description of the most relevant research and methodological works in this area from the point of view of musical education.*

Research methods. *In the disclosure of the main positions of the work, theoretical analysis, musical-critical, intonational, performing methods of research were used.*

Research results. *The article opens upon one of the most crucial spheres of musical education and national musicology – children's piano music. The research and generalization of scientific literature accumulated over fifty years indicate the need for thorough analyze of piano music for children of composers of Uzbekistan.*

Practical application. *Piano music for children occupies a significant area in the creation of Uzbek composers. In their children's piano opuses, modern Uzbek composers rely on the experience of Western European and Russian composers, as well as on the achievements of composers representing the older generation of the national school of composition.*

Keywords: *Uzbekistan, children's piano music, composer, musicology, musical education, musical upbringing.*

Introduction. Music plays a significant role in a child's life. The great teacher V.A. Sukhomlinsky expressed the honorable idea that "music is the most miraculous, the most delicate way of attracting goodness, beauty, humanity" [1,

p.39]. In the research of national musicologists, theorists and historians of musical art, there is currently no complete catalog of piano opuses created for children, there is no systematization of musical material by chronology, composers, genres, styles. We received the earliest information about children's music only in the form of mentions or a short excursion in scientific articles devoted to chamber music.

Materials and methods. Thus, in the article “The Birth of the Chamber Genre” [2, pp. 243-247], the excellent Uzbek researcher T.Vyzgo determined that the first opuses of Uzbek piano compositions that entered the children’s repertoire were easy pieces in terms of piano texture for two-handed and four-handed performance by V. Uspensky¹, which are arrangements of spoken-professional melodies - "Miskin II", "Muhammas Iraq", "Sauti Ajam", "Samoi Dugoh", "Askari" [3, p. 381] and other pieces of the traditional repertoire. These pieces were recorded by V.Uspensky mainly from the professional singer and musician Shorahim Shoumarov during the period of collecting material for the musical drama “Farhad and Shirin”. At the same time, T.Vyzgo rightly describes as B.Nadezhdin also a founding composer in the sphere of children's piano music. As remarked by the scientist, collections for beginning pianists: Children's Pieces for Piano (1939), Ten Pieces for Piano (1948), Children's Album for Piano (1948), Fifteen Children's Pieces for Piano (1947), Three Children's Pieces for Piano (1948) and a number of other collections were composed by the creator based on the author's own idea. There are almost no direct borrowings in them, but the general style of the music reflects the modal intonation and rhythmic features of Uzbek folklore. The appearance of B.B.Nadezhdin’s collections made it possible to introduce piano composition based on the melodic material of Uzbek music into pedagogical practice [2, pp. 243-244].

In 1968, the first major scientific article appeared, specifically devoted to piano music, including children's music - the work of V.Golovina "Piano Creativity of Composers of Uzbekistan" [4, pp. 164-179]. V.Golovina points out that during

¹ Two notebooks of piano pieces by Uspensky for two-handed and four-handed performance were published in the form of two collections in 1936 in Tashkent.

the period of formation of professional musical culture in Uzbekistan, piano music played a definite role in the process of formation of national style. She notes that a characteristic feature of the development of piano music is the attraction towards folk song sources and the desire to connect elements of Uzbek folk music with professional traditions, and the basis of the overwhelming majority of piano works by V.Uspensky, B.Nadezhdin, G.Mushel, B.Gienko, H.Izamov, Ik.Akbarov, L.Nikolaev, M.Ashrafi are the intonations, rhythms and modes of Uzbek folk music.

The prominent Uzbek scholar N.Yanov-Yanovskaya in her fundamental article “Piano Music” [5, pp. 329-347] examined in detail the piano pieces of V.Uspensky, G.Mushel, B.Nadezhdin, B.Gienko, B.Zeidman and the piano music of the first Uzbek composers – H.Izamov, M.Ashrafi, H.Azimov, Ik.Akbarov, P.Khalikov, A.Khalimov. N.Yanov-Yanovskaya noted that in Uzbekistan, piano music as a genre was formed in the post-war period and consists mainly of piano miniatures based on Uzbek national grounds, in which everyday song intonations and genre-dance images predominate.

In the period of the 1970s and 1980s, piano compositions were distinguished by a deepening of imagery and an expansion of the genre range [6, p. 203] – the polyphonic cycle of G.Mushel “24 Preludes and Fugues”, the cycle of D.Saidaminova “Walls of Ancient Bukhara”, the cycle “Replicas” by N.Narkhodzhaev, sonatas by N.Zakirov, “Rubai” by B.Gienko, etc. In the article “Piano Music,” national musicologist N.Kadyrova [6, pp. 203-217] analyzes the above-mentioned works, and also draws attention to children’s piano music – the Album of Piano Pieces for the Children’s Music School by B. Gienko. Each piece in the collection has an expressive programmatic title: “Hot Noon”, “Catch Up!”, “Cheerful Doira”, “Tanbur and Doira”, etc. N.Kadyrova notes the composer’s desire for clear texture, subtlety of musical language and the focus of music on children’s perception [6, p. 215].

Results and Discussion. Today, piano teaching for children with its “educational” focus is an accessible, effective source in the musical education of children, and children’s music and art schools are of great importance in this complex and lengthy process. In art schools, not only future professional pianists receive piano education, but also students of other departments - children studying in the departments of string, wind and percussion instruments, in the departments of folk instruments, departments of academic, pop and traditional singing, as well as all those wishing to join the art of piano. It is worth recalling the words of the leading musicologist I.Karelova, that the opportunity for thousands of children to learn the beautiful art of music supports – first and foremost – as a guarantee of raising the entire cultural level of the population of our republic [7, p. 286-287].

In the piano class, children get acquainted with the pieces of foreign and Uzbek composers of various genres and styles and develop their musical intellection. The modern work program for the special piano class for the Children's School of Music establish a number of requirements aimed at improving the quality of upbringing and education processes. Musical upbringing is the process of forming the musical culture of an individual in his spiritual, mental, physical, aesthetic, artistic education in the formation of personal qualities of a person, and musical education is aimed at the adoption and formation of specific musical knowledge, skills and abilities. This is how R.Kadyrov defines these significant concepts [1, p.35].

An essential aspect of musical education is the presence of chrestomathies on piano repertoire and collections of works by composers of Uzbekistan. One of the first blightly composers and teachers who turned their attention to the creation of national methodological literature was H.Azimov. The textbook for primary grades of music schools “Fortepiano darsligi” (“Piano Textbook”)² is the first collection for

² The first edition dates back to 1971; the second was published by H. Azimov’s student, R. Yunusov, in 1998.

teaching piano playing in the Uzbek language, and the overwhelming majority of works that constitute this textbook are works by composers of Uzbekistan.

In the teaching environment there is another piano collection for senior students is the Chrestomathy for the Piano Course by S.Spivak and S.Yuldasheva. The compilers relied on the music of Uzbek composers, in whose pieces nationally determined stylistic features and the modal sphere of Uzbek melodies are widely combined with traditional piano genres of European music [8, p. 3]. The collection includes inventions by P.Khalikov, preludes and fugues by G.Mushel, pieces of large form - cycles by N.Narkhodzhaev, P.Khalikov and G.Mushel, miniatures by G.Mushel, B.Gienko, S.Varelas, H.Izamov, P.Khalikov.

Among the author's piano collections for children, it is necessary to highlight the piano album "Guldasta" ("Flower Garden" or "Bouquet") by M.Atajanov. The pieces included in the album "Guldasta" (2001) are distinguished by their colorful imagery, melody, and national roots. Using their material, the teacher is given the opportunity to develop not only professional skills and abilities, but also to cultivate the spiritual and moral qualities of the student [9, p. 96].

In all aspects, the young composer M. Mukhtarov should be considered a "children's" composer. Over the past few years, collections of "Piano Pieces for Primary Schools", "Hayvonot bog'i" ("Musical Zoo"), "Yangi kun" ("New Day"), "So'zsiz izhor" ("Confession Without Words"), and "12 Waltzes" have been published. M.Mukhtarov proposed his own version of European-monodic synthesis not only in the form of an organic combination of stylistic and genre elements, but also at a more complex form-generating level, which reflects modern trends in the composer's creativity in Uzbekistan [10, p. 103].

Conclusion. Modern national composers - R.Abdullaev, H.Rakhimov, V.Saparov, A.Mansurov, M.Atajanov, O.Abdullaeva, A.Safarov, Z.Khodieva, Sh.Sobirov, M.Mukhtarov - in their children's piano pieces rely on the experience of Western European and Russian composers, as well as on the achievements of composers

representing the older generation of the national composer school - B.Nadezhdin, Ik.Akbarov, H.Azimov, G.Mushel, B.Gienko. Being in line with the general process of development of composer creativity in Uzbekistan, children's piano music reflects approaches to the adaptation of European genres of piano music on Uzbek musical basis, the desire for a synthesis of national and European musical language [10, p.97].

References:

1. Kadyrov R.G. Musical pedagogy: Textbook. – Tashkent: Musiqa, 2009. – 504 p., ill., notes.
2. History of Uzbek Soviet music. In 2 volumes. Volume 1 (1917-1945) / Ed. collective: T.S.Vyzgo and others. – T.: Publishing house of literature and art named after Gafur Gulyam, 1972. – 384 p.
3. Uspensky V.A. Articles, memoirs, letters / Comp. I.A. Akbarov – T.: Publishing House of Literature and Art, 1980. – 384 p.
4. Golovina V.A. Piano music of composers of Uzbekistan // Essays on the history of musical culture of Uzbekistan / Ed. M.S.Kovbas. Issue I. - T.: "Ўқитувчи", 1968. - P.164-179.
5. History of Uzbek Soviet music. In 2 volumes. Volume 2 (1945-1967) / Ed. collective: T.S.Vyzgo et al. – T.: Publishing house of literature and art named after Gafur Gulyam, 1973. – 376 p.
6. History of Uzbek Soviet music. Vol.3 (1968-1984) / Ed.: T.S.Vyzgo et al. – T.: Publishing house of literature and art named after Gafur Gulyam, 1991. – 280 p.
7. Karelova I.N. Musical education in Uzbekistan // Issues of musical culture of Uzbekistan. / Ed. and compiled by I.N. Karelova. - Tashkent: Publishing house of literature and art named after Gafur Gulyam, 1961. - 312 p.
8. Spivak S.P., Yuldasheva S.Kh. Chrestomathy for piano courses. Part 2: For students of the Faculty of Music and Pedagogy and music-pedagogical secondary school / Introduced author. – Tashkent: "O'qituvchi", 1981. – 157 p.

9. Galushchenko I.G. On the piano music of Muhammadzhan Atajanov // Science and education today / Olimp Publishing House, 2021. - pp. 96-97
10. Sidikova A.M. Collection of Mekhrozha Mukhtarov “Piano pieces for junior grades”: experience of analysis // Problems of modern science and education. – M., 2023. – No. 3. – P.97-103. <http://ipi1.ru/images/PDF/2023/181/sbornik-mekhrozha.pdf>